

NANOENGINEERED HIERARCHICAL CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES WITHOUT FIBER STRENGTH LOSS

R. Li^{1*}, P. Florin¹, S. A. Steiner III², B. L. Wardle¹

¹Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA 02139, USA,

²Department of Materials Science and Engineering and Biological Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA 02139, USA

*Corresponding author (richli@mit.edu)

Keywords: *CNT-grafted, carbon fiber, fuzzy fiber, hierarchical composites, nanoengineered*

1 General Introduction

Advanced filamentary composite architectures that incorporate hierarchical fibers sheathed with radially-aligned arrays of high-aspect-ratio carbon nanotubes (CNTs)—so-called “fuzzy fiber” reinforced plastics (FFRPs)—have been demonstrated to enable significant improvements in fracture toughness [1], interlaminar shear strengths [2], and multifunctional properties [3] critical to widening the performance envelopes and applications of traditional aerospace composites. To date, however, development of carbon fiber-based FFRPs (CFFRPs) in which in-plane mechanical properties are also preserved has been challenging. Growth of CNTs on carbon fibers via chemical vapor deposition (CVD) has to date only been achieved at the expense of significant strength loss—up to 55% [4]. Additionally, since carbon fiber substrates exhibit poor wettability towards typical CNT growth catalyst materials, prior attempts at growing CNTs on carbon fibers (CFs) have typically used detrimental surface treatments such as acid or electrochemical etching in order to achieve high-yield nanotube growth which can also cause fiber surface pitting and dissolution. Together these two problems substantially diminish in-plane strength of resultant hierarchical composites. A novel method for high-yield growth of CNTs on CFs that does not result in reduced fiber tensile strength is presented and for the first time enables advanced CNT/CF hierarchical composites with preserved in-plane mechanical properties. A scalable, non-covalent functionalization technique coupled with a low temperature CNT growth process was demonstrated to be effective at maintaining fiber strengths using single-fiber mechanical tests. Successful scale-up and tensile testing of unidirectional CFFRP specimens prepared using this technique are presented here and the ply-level properties of these nanoengineered composites are assessed.

2 Strategies for Preserving CF Properties

2.1 Non-Covalent Functionalization via K-PSMA

In order to achieve high-yield CNT growth on CFs without compromising filamentary properties, a non-covalent functionalization method was developed to improve CF wettability towards CNT catalyst precursor solutions. Previous work has demonstrated the efficacy of non-covalent coatings based on 1.5 wt % hydrolyzed polystyrene-*alt*-maleic anhydride (h-PSMA) [7][8] for functionalizing CFs with carboxylic acid moieties without degrading fiber strength [9]. By preparing a polyelectrolyte from h-PSMA, a new functional coating, potassium polystyrene-*alt*-maleic acid (K-PSMA), was found to facilitate iron catalyst ion (Fe^{3+}) adhesion onto CF surfaces without detrimental surface treatments [1]. In a typical experiment, a 0.25 wt % K-PSMA dip-coating solution was prepared as follows. A solution of 1.4 grams of polystyrene-*alt*-maleic anhydride (PSMA) in 25 mL of acetone was gradually mixed with 300mL 0.3M aqueous sodium hydroxide, stirred for 3 hours, and acidified with 0.1M nitric acid to a pH of 8. Acetone was rotary evaporated out of the solution and potassium carbonate was added until a pH of 11 was attained. Finally, water was added to yield 0.25 wt % K-PSMA.

The unsized (i.e., never-been-sized) TohoTenax HTR-40 24K tow was selected as the CF substrate to prevent possible introduction of damage from desizing a sized product. Tow segments were dip-coated in 0.25 wt % K-PSMA solution for 5 min., spread over smooth rollers to ensure uniform coating, and subjected to drying under vacuum pressure of 91 kPa at $\sim 80^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 minutes while under low tension to preserve collimation.

2.2 Catalyst Deposition

The K-PSMA functionalized tow was dip-coated for 5 min in a catalyst solution of 0.05M

$\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in isopropanol that had been mixed and stirred for 1 hour. Subsequently, the tow was dried under vacuum pressure of 91 kPa at $\sim 80^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 minutes.

2.3 Low-Temperature CNT growth

Previous in-depth heat treatment studies demonstrate that typical thermal CVD temperatures for CNT growth at $\sim 730^\circ\text{C}$ correlate to large CF strength loss in inert environments [9]. Further in-depth heat treatment studies on the same CF substrates revealed a threshold temperature for fiber strength reduction [6]. As a result, a low-temperature thermal CVD via oxidative dehydrogenation of acetylene and carbon dioxide was implemented at 480°C [8], enabling high-yield CNT growth below the threshold temperature above which CF damage occurs. $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{K-PSMA}$ dip-coated tows were placed inside a fused quartz tube (25 mm OD, 22 mm ID, 30 cm length) housed inside a Lindberg/Blue M MiniMite furnace. After flushing the tube and lines for 2 minutes with 750 sccm of Ar, H_2 was introduced at 400 sccm, Ar reduced to 200 sccm, and the temperature ramped to 480°C . Once at set point temperature, H_2/Ar were turned off before flowing CO_2 as well as a 10% C_2H_2 in Ar mixture for 15 minutes at 17 sccm and 167 sccm respectively. During cool down, Ar was once again flushed through the tube at 750 sccm.

2.4 CNT Growth Results

Scanning electron microscopy (JEOL 6060) reveals CNT lengths averaging 1-2 microns (Figures 1 and 2). Additionally, circumferential growth was observed around individual fibers indicating that the 0.25 wt % K-PSMA function coating is effective at allowing iron catalyst adhesion, thus successfully forming a fuzzy carbon fiber tow.

Fig. 1. 1500X magnified SEM image of HTR-40 coated with $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{K-PSMA}$ and CVD processed at 480°C

Fig. 2. 2300X magnified SEM image of HTR-40 coated with $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{K-PSMA}$ and CVD processed at 480°C

2.5 Single Filament Mechanical Testing Results

To assess the effects of the applied polymer coating and low temperature CVD on fiber tensile properties, single filament testing was conducted for CVD processed fuzzy HTR-40 fibers as well as baseline as-received HTR-40 fibers. In accordance with the ASTM D3379 [12] standard, samples with 25 mm gauge length were strained at 400 $\mu\text{strain/s}$, and loads were measured in the MTS UTM Nano tensile tester. Weibull distributions [15] for both baseline and fuzzy CF are plotted in Figure 3 and indicate no strength degradation from CNT growth [6].

Fig. 3. Fitted Weibull Distributions of Baseline and Fuzzy CF single filament strengths [6].

3 Scale-up to Unidirectional Composite Samples

3.1 Fuzzy Carbon Fiber Composite Fabrication at High Fiber Volume Fraction

In order to assess the effects of CNT presence on in-plane properties of aerospace composites, both unsize as-received tows and fuzzy CF tows were impregnated with the Hexcel RTM 6 aerospace grade resin system for unidirectional composite testing. Whereas impregnated tow standards of ISO 10618 [13] and SACMA 16R-94 [14] were studied, the ASTM D4018 [10] was selected for its widespread use by the carbon fiber manufacturer. Further, to directly compare experimental values with aerospace composites, specimen fiber volume fractions (V_f) must be fabricated to high values typically used in the industry (~60%). A resin impregnation process was developed as follows: Tows were tensioned lightly (to maintain collimation) and inserted into a Teflon groove. A Teflon plug was then slowly lowered into the groove (Figure 4), thus forming a channel surrounding the tow that will be infused with resin – effectively constraining the specimen V_f [16].

The tow and mold assembly was then sealed and vacuumed in a resin infusion table (Figure 5). Both the table and a resin source were heated to 90 degrees Celsius while the table vacuum was adjusted to a gauge pressure of 93 kPa. Next, the table inlet valve was opened to initiate infusion through the Teflon channel. Once resin reached past the channel exit, the valve was closed off and the table was

subjected to curing at 160°C for 75 min., and 180°C for 120 min.

Fig. 4. Teflon plug is lined up with the lip of the groove (left) before being lowered into the groove (right). A channel is thus formed for resin infusion [16].

Fig. 5. Resin Infusion Table Setup. Resin flows from source/valve on left through the channel and exits to vacuum on right.

Specimens were subsequently extracted by separating Teflon mold halves, yielding a CF V_f of ~67%. Tabbing in accordance with ASTM D4018 was then achieved by gluing the impregnated tow within a thermoset epoxy layer bounded by sandpaper (Figure 6). Tabs were separated by a gauge length of 150 mm and final sample cross section dimensions were 1.25 mm wide by 1.15 mm tall.

Fig. 6. Final 67% V_f Tabbed Unidirectional Composite Tensile Specimen

3.2 Fuzzy Carbon Fiber Composite Testing

Testing was conducted on the Instron 1332 load frame with load measured from a 220 kN capacity cell. Sample surfaces were spray painted white and speckled with black ink prior to being placed between grips at 2.1 MPa. An optical camera acquired sample images every 250 ms and a synchronized load measurement was taken while the sample was strained 1mm/min until failure. Strain values were then calculated utilizing the Vic2D™ software towards the center of the specimen. A typical stress-strain curve is shown in Figure 7 exhibiting the increasing modulus of strain as general observed for ex-PAN-based carbon fibers [17].

Fig. 7. Typical composite stress-strain curve for baseline unidirectional specimen with $V_f = 67\%$.

4 Tensile Testing Results for High Fiber Volume Fraction Specimens ($V_f = 67\%$).

In accordance with the ASTM D4018 standard, implied fiber stress values were determined for both high fiber volume fraction baseline (CFRP) and

fuzzy fiber (CFFRP) specimens. Figure 8 reproduces previously reported values [16] of 3 samples for each subset.

It was found that implied fiber chord modulus values were preserved as was consistent with single filament testing results [6]. Implied fiber strength values demonstrate a slight decrease in the means of 7%. Because single fiber results indicate a preservation of fiber strength, it was hypothesized that damage may be introduced during the manufacturing of composite specimens. As fibers were transversely compressed to high fiber volume fractions of 67% (low inter-fiber distances), high transverse stresses [21] may induce fiber damage as Teflon mold halves were brought together.

Fig. 8. Implied longitudinal fiber modulus (top) and fiber strength (bottom) values from unidirectional composite specimens. Three data points were taken for each subset [16].

Therefore, it is important to perform a study that decouples this manufacturing effect by fabricating specimens with minimal transverse compression via low fiber volume fraction specimens.

5. Low Fiber Volume Fraction Study ($V_f = 37\%$)

5.1 Low Fiber Volume Fraction Specimen Fabrication

To eliminate transverse compression on fuzzy CF tows, new Teflon molds were precision machined with a larger infusion channel designed for a fiber volume fraction of 37%. This newly targeted volume fraction was selected by considering effective fuzzy fiber diameters (including CNT lengths) and realistic packing scenarios that would ensure no transverse stresses to arise from Teflon mold compaction. All other fabrication steps were retained to provide comparable testing specimens. The same unsized CF 24K tow was impregnated.

Because of the larger channel areas formed by the Teflon molds, infusion characteristics have drastically changed. An experimental parametric study was implemented, investigating the effects of infusion vacuum levels, resin flow throttling via inclusion of porous medium within the table, diversion of air pockets, and pulsated vacuum on the quality of the resultant part. Samples were inspected for any surface defects, which were subsequently filled in with two part epoxy systems to relieve stress concentrations. Resultant specimens have cross sectional dimensions of 1.15 mm by 2.2 mm while gauge lengths between tabs are held at 150 mm.

Fig. 9. Final 37% V_f Tabbed Unidirectional Composite Tensile Specimen

5.2 Low Fiber Volume Fraction Tensile Testing Result

3 low V_f CFRP and 1 CFFRP specimens were tested utilizing the same loading conditions outlined for the high V_f samples. ASTM D4018 stipulates the successful testing of a minimum of 4 samples that fail away from the specimen tabs. As a result, the following presented results should be considered preliminary.

Implied fiber stress values were once again calculated to generate implied fiber modulus and implied fiber strengths.

Fig. 10. Implied longitudinal fiber modulus (top) and fiber strength (bottom) values from low volume fraction unidirectional composite specimens. Three data points were taken for CFRP and one was obtained for CFFRP specimens.

Implied fiber modulus values for low volume fractions samples were consistent and within range of each other. Once again in-plane elastic properties of fuzzy carbon fiber composites are maintained. Additionally, these values were consistent with high volume fraction samples. Given the low CNT volume fraction embedded within the matrix, it is expected from rule of mixtures [18] that no significant composite modulus changes will be observed.

Implied strength values indicate a significant drop in mean baseline strengths at low fiber volume fractions. Given the change of infusion properties with low volume fraction baseline samples, possible manufacturing related defects will be investigated and addressed in future work.

Particularly noteworthy from the 37% V_f CFFRP sample is the high implied fiber strength value. While this result is preliminary, Figure 11 shows that this value is not only above the high V_f baseline mean, but also beyond the range of any tested high fiber volume fraction CFFRP. Further tensile testing of low volume fraction CFFRP is ongoing and will further assess the effect of CNT growth on the in-

plane strength of the resultant hierarchical composite.

Fig. 11. Implied Fiber Strengths comparing 37% V_f CFFRP with 67% V_f Specimens.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

The presented strategies enable CNT growth on CF without harmful fiber surface modifications and high temperature CVD that degrade CF load carrying capabilities. Single fiber testing results previously confirmed that tensile properties of individual fuzzy carbon fibers were preserved, and scale-up to unidirectional CFFRP specimens at targeted fiber volume fractions was demonstrated. The successful fabrication procedure for high fiber volume fraction specimens ($V_f = 67\%$) enabled initial ply-level mechanical characterization, demonstrating a slight decrease in implied fiber mean strengths [16]. However, to decouple manufacturing induced fiber damage, an additional low volume fraction ($V_f = 37\%$) study was demonstrated here. Preliminary tests reveal unresolved manufacturing issues with low volume fraction baseline samples that will be addressed in future work. However, preliminary CFFRP at 37% shows composite strength within range of 67% baseline samples. In addition to ongoing tensile tests, fuzzy fiber-matrix adhesion characterizations [19][20] are currently being conducted. Future work on these hierarchical

composite specimens includes multifunctional enhancement measurements (e.g., electrical conductivities). Further scale-up of the CFFRP manufacturing onto carbon fiber weaves will also be implemented to evaluate improvements in interlaminar properties.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Mark Payne for full assistance with specimen manufacturing; Peter Shpik of the TohoTenax Corporation for his valuable collaboration and donation of carbon fiber; Sunny Wicks (MIT) and Jeonyoon Lee for assistance with resin infusion; John Kane (MIT) and Dr. Ethan Parsons (MIT) for optical strain mapping setups; and Todd Billings (MIT) for precision machining of molds and jigs. This work was supported by Boeing, EADS, Embraer, Lockheed Martin, Saab AB, Composite Systems Technology, Hexcel, and TohoTenax through MIT's Nano-Engineered Composite aerospace Structures (NECST) Consortium. This work made use of the Shared Experimental Facilities supported in part by the MRSEC Program of the National Science Foundation under award number DMR-0819762 and also made use of the core facilities at the Institute for Soldier Nanotechnologies at MIT, supported by the U.S. Army Research Office under contract W911NF-07-D-0004.

References

- [1] S. Wicks, R. Guzmán de Villoria, B. L. Wardle "Interlaminar and Intralaminar Reinforcement of Composite Laminates with Aligned Carbon Nanotubes". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 70, No. 1, 2010, pp. 20-28.
- [2] E. J. Garcia, B. L. Wardle, A. J. Hart, N. Yamamoto "Fabrication and Multifunctional Properties of a Hybrid Laminate with Aligned Carbon Nanotubes Grown In Situ". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 68, 2008, pp. 2034-2041.
- [3] R. Guzman de Villoria, N. Yamamoto, A. Miravete, B. L. Wardle "Multi-physics damage sensing in nano-engineered structural composites". *Nanotechnology*; Vol. 22, 2011.
- [4] H. Qian, A. Bismarck, E. S. Greenhalgh, G. Kalinka, M. S. P. Shaffer, "Hierarchical Composites Reinforced with Carbon Nanotube Grafted Fibers: The Potential Assessed at the Single Fiber Level," *Chemistry of Materials*, Vol. 20, 2008, pp. 1862-1869.
- [5] S. A. Steiner III (2011). *Carbon nanotube Growth on Challenging Substrates: Applications for Carbon-Fiber Composites*. Ph.D. Thesis. Massachusetts Institute of Technology: U.S.A.
- [6] ACS Applied Materials and Interface Paper Steiner III, S.A., Li, R., Wardle, B.L., "Circumventing the Mechanochemical Origins of Strength Loss in the Synthesis of Hierarchical Carbon Fibers" *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces*, 2013.
- [7] A. Carrillo et al., "Non-Covalent Functionalization of Graphite and Carbon Nanotubes with Polymer Multilayers and Gold Nanoparticles," *Nano Letters*, Vol. 3, No. 20, 2003, pp. 1437-1440.
- [8] A. D. Strook, R. S. Kane, M. Weck, S. J. Metallo, G. M. Whitesides "Synthesis of Free-Standing Quasi-Two-Dimensional Polymers," *Langmuir*, Vol. 19, 2003, pp. 2466-2472
- [9] S. A. Steiner III, R. Li, R. Guzmán de Villoria, M. S. Tsai, and B. L. Wardle "Methods for Growing Carbon Nanotubes on Carbon Fibers that Preserve Fiber Tensile Strength" AIAA-2010-2641, *51st AIAA Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials (SDM) Conference*, Orlando, FL, April 12-15, 2010.
- [10] A. Magrez, J. W. Seo, R. Smajda, B. Korbely, J. C. Andresen, M. Mionic, S. Casimirius, L. Forro "Low-Temperature, Highly Efficient Growth of Carbon Nanotubes on Functional Materials by an Oxidative Dehydrogenation Reaction". *ACS Nano* 2010, 4.
- [11] ASTM International "Standard Test Method for Tensile Strength and Young's Modulus for High-Modulus Single-Filament Materials". *ASTM D3379-75, 1989*.
- [12] ASTM International "Standard Test Method for Properties of Continuous Filament Carbon and Graphite Fiber Tows". *ASTM D4018-99, 2008*.
- [13] International Standards Organization, *Carbon fibre-Determination of tensile properties of resin-impregnated yarn*, ISO 10618, 2004.
- [14] Suppliers of Advanced Composite Materials Association, *SACMA Recommended Method for Tow Tensile Testing of Carbon Fibers*, SRM 16R-94, 1994.
- [15] Hitchon, J. W.; Phillips, D. C., "The Dependence of the Strength of Carbon Fibres on Length," *Fibre Science and Technology*, Vol. 12, 1979, pp. 217-233.
- [16] Li, R., Steiner III, S.A., Florin, P., Wardle, B.L.. "CNT-grafted Carbon Fibers with Preserved Tensile Properties Assessed at the Single Fiber and Unidirectional Composite Scales" AIAA-2013, 54th AIAA Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials (SDM) Conference, Boston, MA April, 2013.
- [17] Dresselhaus, M. S.; Dresselhaus, G.; Sugihara, K.; Spain, I. L.; Goldberg, H. A., *Graphite Fibers and Filaments*, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1988.

- [18] Cebeci, H., Guzman de Villoria, R., Hart, A. J., Wardle, B. L., "Multifunctional properties of high volume fraction aligned carbon nanotube polymer composites with controlled morphology", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 69, 2009, pp. 2649-2656.
- [19] Lachman, N., Carey, B. J., Hashim, D. P., Ajayan, P. M., Wagner, H. D., "Application of continuously-monitored single fiber fragmentation tests to carbon nanotube/carbon microfiber hybrid composites", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 72, 2012, pp. 1711-1717.
- [20] Kepple, K. L.; Sanborn, G. P.; Lacasse, P. A.; Gruenberg, K. M.; Ready, W. J., "Improved Fracture Toughness Of Carbon Fiber Composite Functionalized With Multi Walled Carbon Nanotubes," *Carbon*, Vol. 46, No. 15, 2008, pp. 2026-2033.
- [21] Lomov, S.V., V. Koissin, M. Karahan, A. Godara, I. Gorbatiikh, I. Verpoest. *Compressibility of CNT-Grafted Fibrous Reinforcements: A Theory*. *Int J Mater Form* 2010: France. Vol. 3. pp. 627-630